

PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE AND DELAMINATION IN COMPOSITES BY THE ELEMENT-FAILURE APPROACH AND STRAIN INVARIANT FAILURE THEORY (SIFT)

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SUMMARY: The element-failure concept, originally proposed for simulating dynamic crack propagation in isotropic materials, is a potentially powerful and practical method for the modelling of damage, fracture and delamination in fibre-reinforced composite laminates. When a crack or damage is propagating within an element, the element is deemed to have partially failed, but not removed from the computations. Consequently, only a fraction of the stresses that were computed before the damage entered the element contribute to the nodal forces of the element. In isotropic materials, this treatment of crack propagation allows fracture paths within individual elements and is able to accommodate crack growth in any arbitrary direction without the need for remeshing. However, the concept is especially useful when extended to composite structures because the nature of damage in composite laminates is generally diffused, characterized by multiple matrix cracks, fibre pullout, fibre breakage and delaminations. It is usually not possible to even identify crack tips in the fashion of traditional fracture mechanics. Since parts of a damaged composite structure are often able to partially transmit load despite the presence of some damage, it is advantageous to model the damaged portions with partially failed elements. The damage may be efficiently modeled and tracked using element-failure concepts, with the application of appropriate failure criteria and damage evolution laws. The idea is to embody the effects of damage into the effective nodal forces of the finite element. In this paper, we report the novel use of element-failure concepts with the Strain Invariant Failure Theory (SIFT) in the prediction of damage progression in composite laminated structures. Specifically, the initiation and propagation of damage and delaminations in a three-point bend test and a cross-ply laminate with a central hole are analyzed. The results show qualitative agreement with experimental observation when the element-failure approach is used with SIFT. Other methods of modelling damage such as element removal or material property degradation are also studied, but the correlation with experimental results in these cases is not as good. Issues such as possible interpenetration of delamination surfaces and admissibility of solutions are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: element-failure, strain invariant failure theory, nodal force modification, progressive damage, delamination, fracture

INTRODUCTION

The element-failure algorithm was originally proposed by Beissel *et al* [1] for modelling dynamic crack propagation *within* the elements of a finite element (FE) mesh. When a

crack is propagating within an element, the element is deemed to have partially failed and is not removed from the finite element computations. However, only a fraction of the stresses that were computed before the crack tip entered the element contribute to the nodal forces of the element. This fraction is dependent on the crack length within the element. When the crack has propagated *through* the element, the element is completely failed but is still not removed from the mesh and can only resist volumetric compression. The advantage of this treatment of dynamic crack propagation in isotropic materials is that it allows crack growth in any arbitrary direction (with the aid of suitable fracture criteria) without the need for remeshing.

However, the element-failure concept is particularly suited for failure analysis of composite structures, where certain modes of failure do not completely preclude the ability of the composite material to sustain stresses. Generally, damage evolution in composite materials is complicated and may involve multiple failure modes, such as fibre breakage, fibre pullout, delamination between plies, matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, etc., which have strong interactions with one another. It is usually not possible to clearly identify and define cracks or crack tips in the sense of conventional fracture mechanics (Fig. 1). In some exceptional situations, a crack may be defined, such as in the case of a single delamination in a laboratory fracture test specimen. However, even in these situations, mechanisms such as fibre bridging across the crack surfaces, delamination kinking or branching into other fracture planes often greatly complicate analysis by the fracture mechanics approach [2]. Recently, an explicit element-failure algorithm for composites has been used successfully to analyze damage and delamination propagation in low-velocity impact of composite laminates [3]. An advantage of this analysis is that it eliminates the need to use contact algorithms to ensure that interpenetration of delamination surfaces does not occur, because the failed elements are not removed from the finite element computations.

Fig.1 Model of (a) fracture in isotropic materials and (b) damage in composite materials

In this paper, we have adapted the element-failure concept for the two-dimensional and three-dimensional *implicit* FE method. We illustrate the use of the element-failure concept in two cases of progressive damage analysis of composites: the failure of a composite laminate loaded under three-point bend, and the damage propagating from the edge of a hole in a composite cross-ply laminate under monotonically increasing tensile far-field load. Two other commonly used methods for modelling progressive damage in composites are by removing elements and selectively degrading the mechanical properties of the

material. These are also used in this paper for the purpose of comparing the damage patterns predicted by each method. Two failure criteria are employed in the damage prediction, the Tsai-Wu failure theory [4] and the Strain Invariant failure theory (SIFT), which is a new micromechanics-based failure theory for composites proposed by Gosse [5] and is reportedly used extensively by the Boeing Aircraft Co. Due to space constraints, the description of this theory is not given here, although it should be mentioned that failure is determined by considering the criticality of three strain invariant values. These invariants have been “amplified” through micromechanical analysis. The first of the invariants is related to J_1 , the second related to the von Mises strain with micromechanical amplification factors extracted in the matrix, and the third also related to von Mises strain but with micromechanical amplification factors extracted within the fiber or at the fiber-matrix interface.

ELEMENT-FAILURE METHOD FOR COMPOSITES

The concept of element-failure for fiber-reinforced polymeric composites is described here. The central idea and assumption is that the effects of damage on the mechanical behaviour can be essentially described by the effective nodal forces of a finite element. The manner by which these effects of damage translate to the effective nodal forces will in general depend upon the damage evolution law appropriate to the local mode of damage experienced by the composite material, as well as the FE formulation. For the purpose of illustration, consider an FE of a virgin (undamaged) composite material (Fig.2 (a)), experiencing a set of nodal forces. Suppose damage in the form of transverse matrix microcracks are formed (which may or may not be uniformly distributed within the FE), the load-carrying capacity of the FE will be compromised, very likely in a directionally and spatially dependent manner (Fig.2 (b)). In conventional material degradation models, this

Fig.2 The element-failure or force modification method

reduction in load-carrying capacity is achieved by reducing or zeroing certain pertinent material stiffness properties of the damaged finite element. In the element-failure method however, the reduction is effected by applying a set of *external* nodal forces such that the *nett internal* nodal forces of elements adjacent to the damaged element are reduced or zeroed (the latter if complete failure or fracture is implied (Fig.2 (c))). The decision whether to fail an element is guided by a suitable failure theory and in each step, only one or two

elements are failed at a time. The “correct” or required set of applied nodal forces to achieve the reduction within each step is determined by successive iterations until the nett internal nodal forces (residuals) of the adjacent elements converge to the desired values. Typically, less than 20 iterations are required and convergence is guaranteed. Note that it is not the internal nodal forces of the damaged element that is zeroed (for the case of complete failure (Fig.2 (c)), but the nett internal nodal forces of adjacent elements. Thus the “stresses” within the failed element no longer have physical meaning although compatibility may be preserved. This process leaves the original (undamaged) material stiffness properties unchanged, and is thus computationally efficient as every step and iteration is simply an analysis with the updated set of loading conditions at the nodes. For this reason, it may also be called the nodal force modification method. Hence, no reformulation of the FE stiffness matrix is necessary.

DAMAGE PROGRESSION IN A THREE-POINT BEND SPECIMEN

The element-failure method as described above has been implemented in a two-dimensional plane strain FE scheme. Since the method simply involves nodal force modification, it can be readily implemented in a commercial implicit FE code, in this case ABAQUS.

Three specimens of a graphite-epoxy cross-ply composite were cut from a laminate cured in an autoclave. The lay-up is $[0_3/90_3/0_3/90_3/0_3]$, the 0° direction coinciding with the spanwise direction. Each specimen is 25 mm wide, with a total average thickness of 2.14 mm and simply-supported on cylindrical rollers placed 60 mm apart. The load (displacement control) is applied at midspan through another cylindrical roller, and rubber padding is placed between the specimen surface and roller to prevent premature local crushing (Fig.3).

Fig.3 The three-point bend test and damage in specimen

The damage pattern is quite consistent among the three specimens and is shown in Fig.3. Shortly after the maximum load of about 2 kN is attained, damage propagated rapidly, resulting in final failure. The first sign of damage occurred in the form of local crushing of

the first 0° plys near the point of application of load and the growth of the first delamination at the interface between the first (0°) and second (90°) layers. This is rapidly followed by the initiation and growth of the second delamination at the interface between the third (0°) and fourth (90°) layers. Here, the layers are referred to consecutively from the top surface, as shown in Fig.3; each layer consists of 3 plys of unidirectional tape. After the second delamination has propagated some distance to the right, it kinks into the fourth (90°) layer and continued along the interface with the fifth (0°) layer.

Seven attempts at predicting the damage growth pattern with different combination of methods and failure theories were made (Table 1). The x -direction is defined along the horizontal or spanwise direction, while the y -direction is the out-of-plane direction. The element-failure method is studied with three cases where the x -direction nodal forces are modified; in two cases, they are modified only to 75% and 50% of their original values (EFX75 and EFX50). The rationale for this is that material which has been damaged under compression or crushing still retains some load-bearing capability as debris because of the constraining effects of the surrounding undamaged material.

Table 1 Methods and Failure Theories for prediction of damage progression

Case	Method	Failure theory
EFX75	Element-failure with x -direction nodal forces modified to 75% of original values	SIFT
EFX50	Element-failure with x -direction nodal forces modified to 50% of original values	SIFT
EFX0	Element-failure with x -direction nodal forces zeroed	SIFT
ER	Element-remove	SIFT
MEG	Material property degradation with E_{xx} and G_{xy} zeroed	SIFT
MEG-TW	Material property degradation with E_{xx} and G_{xy} zeroed	Tsai-Wu
MEEG-TW	Material property degradation with E_{xx} , E_{yy} and G_{xy} zeroed	Tsai-Wu

The predicted progressive damage pattern for the case EFX75 is shown in Fig. 4. The qualitative agreement with the observed experimental damage pattern of Fig. 3 is remarkable, given the rather approximate and simplistic method employed. It is seen that the element-failure method, coupled with SIFT, is able to predict the local crushing in the top 0° layer, as well as the first delamination near the interface of the first and second layers. It is also able to predict the onset of the second delamination, although the position at the interface of the fourth and fifth layers is not quite correct. The prediction for EFX50 is not shown as the results are very similar to that of EFX75. Mesh dependency studies have also been conducted but are not reported here. If the x -direction nodal forces are zeroed (EFX0), the damage pattern is altered considerably (Fig.5). The y -direction or through-thickness nodal forces are not zeroed in order to ensure that interpenetration of surfaces between delaminated layers does not occur. Although the first delamination is predicted, subsequent damage is dominated by local material crushing failure below the point of application of load, and no second delamination is predicted. Although approximate, the nodal force modification scheme for EFX75 is more realistic; nonetheless, more sophisticated and systematic nodal force modification schemes may improve the results, in particular to distinguish between extensional (in this case crushing) and shear (interlayer delamination) driven damage modes.

Fig.4 Element-failure and SIFT with x -direction nodal forces modified to 75%

Fig.5 Element-failure and SIFT with x -direction nodal forces zeroed

The prediction by removing elements using SIFT (ER) is not shown because the damage is very localized about the point of application of load, and failure occurred only in the first layer. Damage patterns using material property degradation models are shown in Figs.6 – 8. In Fig.6 (MEG), the modulus E_{xx} (corresponding to E_{11} for the 0° layers and E_{22} for the 90° layers where the 1-direction is along the fibre and 2-direction is transverse) and the shear modulus G_{xy} are zeroed when SIFT predicts failure for the particular element. The predicted damage is quite different from that using element-failure, much of which is initially

congregated at the first (0°) and second (90°) layers. Subsequently, damage is also found in the fourth (90°) layer and tensile failure at the lowest 0° layer.

Fig.6 Material degradation (E_{xx} and G_{xy} zeroed) with SIFT

Figs.7 and 8 show the material property degradation models used with the Tsai-Wu failure theory. Interestingly, the Tsai-Wu theory predicts much less extensive damage than SIFT, and the damage patterns are dramatically different. Furthermore, when both moduli E_{xx} and E_{yy} are set to zero in addition to G_{xy} (Fig.8), the damage pattern changes to that dominated by a series of transverse cracking in the fourth (90°) layer. However, this mode of damage was not observed experimentally. This example emphasizes the point that damage pattern prediction is very sensitive to the stiffness reduction scheme and failure theory.

Fig.7 Material degradation (E_{xx} and G_{xy} zeroed) with Tsai-Wu failure theory

Fig.8 Material degradation (E_{xx} , E_{yy} and G_{xy} zeroed) with Tsai-Wu failure theory

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN A LAMINATE WITH A HOLE

A cross-ply composite laminate with layup $[0_3/90_3]_s$ and a centrally located hole of diameter 5 mm is modeled with three-dimensional FE (ABAQUS). The objective is to track the progression of damage under remote tensile load (along the vertical 0° -direction) using SIFT and the element-failure method. The strain invariants required for SIFT are calculated at each Gauss point of the elements and the values are averaged for each element at the centroid. It is this averaged value that is used for determining criticality using SIFT. The nodal force modification scheme is quite simple: when SIFT predicts failure for a particular element, the net nodal forces from adjacent elements for this node is zeroed only in the direction transverse to the fibre-direction. This presupposes that the first damage to initiate and propagate will be transverse microcracks, not an unreasonable assumption for matrix dominated damage but will probably be inadequate as damage becomes more extensive and

Fig.9 FE meshes for analysis of laminates with holes

severe with localized fibre breakages, splitting, etc. Two FE meshes are used to study the mesh dependency of the predicted results (Fig.9). The first (a) is a radial mesh and the second (b) is a “biased” orthogonal mesh with square elements at the edge of the hole where damage is anticipated.

The damage patterns for the radial mesh in the 90° and the 0° layers are shown in Figs.10 and 11, respectively. The results for the orthogonal mesh are shown in Figs.12 and 13.

Fig.10 Damage progression in the 90° layer for radial mesh

Fig.11 Damage progression in the 0° layer for radial mesh

Fig.12 Damage progression in the 90° layer for orthogonal mesh

Fig.13 Damage progression in the 0° layer for orthogonal mesh

Damage in the 90° and 0° layers initiates at the edge of the hole and propagated outwards. Multiple transverse cracks appear in the 90° layer at the position of maximum stress and grew more extensively away from the edge. The different shades of failed elements correspond to the three strain invariants that have become critical. Subsequent damage in

Fig.14 Typical post-failure pattern in a 0° (outer) layer

the 90° layer moves upwards as well as horizontally. The effect of mesh shape is seen in Figs. 10 and 12. Although the patterns are slightly different, the general trend of growth is similar, and at each damage level, the areas or sizes of damage zones are in close agreement. The same is true for the damage in the 0° layer (Figs. 11 and 13). Here, the damage is initiated at a position slightly off the horizontal axis. It would appear that this damage is predominantly matrix cracking along the fibre (vertical) direction. This would appear to qualitatively agree with experimental observation of post-failure pattern in the 0° layer (Fig.14). Each layer is modeled with only one element in the thickness direction; hence prediction of

delamination is not possible with this FE mesh. A more refined model with multiple elements in the thickness direction will be required if delamination is of interest. However, one readily observes in this analysis that damage in the 0° and 90° layers are intimately related by strong interactions.

CONCLUSION

We have presented a novel and simple approach, called the element-failure or nodal force modification method, to model damage in composite laminates. It assumes that the mechanical effects of damage can be incorporated into effective nodal forces which are then applied to the FE as damage progresses. The method has the advantage that no

elements are removed from the FE mesh and therefore has a mechanism to ensure that interpenetration of crack surfaces does not occur. Furthermore, the material stiffness properties are not altered, ensuring that no recalculation of FE stiffness matrices is necessary. The element-failure method has been applied in this paper with a recent micromechanics-based composite strain invariant failure theory (SIFT) to predict damage pattern evolution for a three-point bend specimen and a laminate with a central hole. It is shown in both cases that there is at least good qualitative agreement with experimentally observed damage patterns. The element removal and material property degradation methods are found to predict significantly different damage patterns. The results are also sensitive to the failure theory or criterion employed.

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REFERENCES

1. Beissel S.R., Johnson G.R., Popelar C.H. "An element-failure algorithm for dynamic crack propagation in general directions", *Engng. Fract. Mechs.*, 61 (3-4), 407-425 (1998).
2. Tay T.E., "Characterization and analysis of delamination fracture in composites – an overview of developments from 1990 to 2001", *Appl. Mechs. Revs.*, 56 (1), 1-32 (2003).
3. Tay T.E., Tan V.B.C. and Deng M., "Element-failure concepts for dynamic fracture and delamination in low-velocity impact of composites", *Int. Jour. of Solids & Structures*, 40 (3), 555-571 (2003).
4. Tsai S.W., *Theory of Composites Design*, Think Composites, Dayton, US (1992).
5. Gosse J.H., "An overview of the Strain Invariant Failure Theory (SIFT)", *Proc. 10th US-Japan Conf. on Composite Materials*, Stanford University, US, 16-18 September (2002) (ed. F-K Chang), DEStech Publications, Lancaster, PA, pp. 989-997.